

Trusted DBL: A Blockchain-based Digital Twin for Sustainable and Interoperable Building Performance Evaluation

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Abstract—Big amount of data produced, exchanged and stored during a building’s lifetime, along with the increasing adoption of IoT technologies, provide a huge potential for the development of data-driven services that can facilitate processes such as predictive maintenance or monitoring of KPIs that are required for demonstrating climate policy compliance. On the other hand, storing and sharing information among interested stakeholders, can generate critical privacy and trust issues. In this paper, we present a blueprint architecture based on a combination of state-of-the-art and disruptive technologies, introducing the concept of a modular Trusted Digital Building Logbook (DBL) that will act as a dynamic record at facility level and will segregate monitored data and other building related information, in a way that guarantees both the privacy of confidential data and the transparency to authorities and city stakeholders that wish to have a real-time overview of buildings’ performance at a local or regional level. The Trusted DBL is based on Blockchain and Digital Twin (DT) technologies and can be used to report progress on emission reductions, the impact of a given energy efficiency measure or to recommend precautionary measures ahead of critical events such as heatwaves. Designed to be interoperable, the Trusted DBLs of different buildings clusters are linked together to capture critical information at national, organizational and/or facility level, help understand a region’s emissions profile and report it in the form of an emissions inventory.

Index Terms—blockchain, digital twins, digital building logbook, climate reporting

I. INTRODUCTION

Buildings in the EU account for the largest share of total final energy consumption (40%) and produce about 36% of all greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions [1]. Compared with other industry sectors, digitalisation and data applications in the building sector are still underdeveloped [2], [3] although their adoption can improve the sustainability performance of buildings and the construction sector [4].

Building DTs are acknowledged for their great potential to digitally transform construction and the built environment [5], [6], [7] and are considered as an evolutionary step of Building Information Modeling (BIM) that can offer integrated, automated and life-cycle approaches [8], [9]. BIM connected with IoT create the basis for the automated data exchange between the physical object and the digital object

that enables real-time performance optimisation of built assets [8]. However, research on performance optimization through real-time assessment of what-if scenarios in Building DTs is still very new and very limited [8], [9], [10].

Blockchain is an emerging technology, which if properly applied in the smart buildings domain can enable stakeholders to tackle the challenges of the industry, such as data reliability, data security and trusted energy accounting [11], [12]. The employment of blockchain and smart contracts for monitoring smart buildings can both enable the digitalization of the buildings management process and assist towards reducing their environmental footprint by pushing climate-related records to energy-efficient blockchain networks. Furthermore, public authorities or any other accredited actor, can be enabled to audit the recorded emissions and issue tokens providing the means for the creation of a decentralized marketplace between building owners, facility managers, construction companies and technology solution providers. The marketplace can be used to provide incentives for carbon-neutral building design, construction, retrofitting and operation [8].

The objective of this paper is to propose a mechanism for the use of private permissioned blockchain networks that enable the unified, systematic, well-organised and standardised storage of building related data across a wider area, city or region (buildings cluster), governed by smart contracts that will automate the process of gathering measurements and reporting them on chain to be accessed by different building value chain actors. This mechanism builds on scalable and interoperable DBLs that combine the application of Blockchain and DT technologies. It facilitates the tokenisation (non-fungible tokens) of energy use and emissions data in buildings and follows open standards, ensuring interoperability between blockchain networks and horizontal auditability and consistency among buildings clusters.

II. BACKGROUND

A. The EU’s Climate Policy and Reporting Mechanism

The recently adopted EU initiatives and strategies are collectively working to accelerate the so-called twin (green and digital) transition. This includes, among others, the Fit for

55 plan, to make the EU's policies fit for reducing net GHG emissions by at least 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels [13] and a policy framework that promotes the development and widespread deployment of digitally enabled solutions that significantly improve the demand-side monitoring of the building stock's environmental, economic and social life-cycle performance [14].

The EU's Climate Monitoring Mechanism sets the EU's own internal reporting rules based on its internationally agreed obligations. It includes a number of components such as projections, policies and measures to cut GHG emissions, national measures to adapt to climate change, low-carbon development strategies etc. It also includes the GHG inventory with emissions of seven GHGs from all sectors [15]. Specific objectives for Quality Assurance and Quality Control to ensure the accuracy, comparability, consistency, completeness, transparency and timeliness of inventories of Member States with regard to the preparation of their GHG inventory are provided through a dedicated EU programme [16]. In practice though, inventories are carried out with top-down methodologies that use aggregated data (statistical ratios) [17].

Local authorities, as leading actors for implementing local sustainable energy policies, play a key role in the achievement of the EU's energy and climate objectives [18]. The Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy covering almost half of the EU population by end of March 2020 [19], is a voluntary movement for local authorities where sustainable energy and climate policies are developed and implemented. Covenant Signatories are provided with a set of methodological principles, procedures and best practices to develop their Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP), in which they document how they will reach their GHG emissions and final energy consumption reduction commitments by 2030. These commitments cover the whole geographical area of the local authority (town, city, region), therefore, committing actions concern both the public and private sectors. However, the local authority is expected to take exceptional measures to what involves its own buildings and facilities, vehicle fleet, etc. Monitoring Reports submitted every second year include an updated Monitoring Emission Inventory (MEI), developed according to the same methods and data sources as the Baseline Emission Inventory (BEI) - for 1990, or the closest subsequent year. It goes without saying that the value of reported emissions to GHG mitigation depends on the quality of data and rigorous calculation [20].

B. Digital Building Logbooks

The introduction of a DBL as a common repository for all relevant data over the entire lifecycle of the building, the strengthening of data collection through an updated Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) framework and potential link with Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) data along with stringent rules on database availability and accessibility was proposed in October 2020 by the Renovation Wave [21]. The aim of DBLs is to facilitate transparency, trust, informed decision making and information sharing within the construction sector,

among building owners and occupants, financial institutions and public authorities [22]. The recent EU funded study for the development of a European Union Framework for DBLs [23] provided the common definition of the role and scope of Digital Building Logbooks, the type of information that could potentially be collected and stored, their sources, the functionalities and the tools applicable to potential users as well as to potential synergies with ongoing EU initiatives like building renovation passports, EPC assessment, Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) of construction products, Level(s), Product Environmental Footprint (PEF), SRI.

C. Digital Building Twins

DTs have been historically used in industrial settings such as the automotive sector. Even if DTs have not yet achieved widespread application in the buildings sector, the key enabling technologies are already in place [24]. Their recent introduction in smart cities contexts, like city logistics [25] and critical infrastructures' security monitoring [26], demonstrates their potential to serve as an integrated modelling, simulation and decision support tool for city stakeholders and urban planners. DTs are enablers for monitoring and managing a building's performance; they support modelling the current and future behaviour of a building or a neighbourhood, under a variety of conditions (weather, climate zone etc.), anticipating energy performance, optimising efficiency, and simulating possible policy interventions aiming to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The PROBONO project [27] for example, develops a cloud-based decision-support and planning tool using DTs for the optimised design of carbon neutral green building neighbourhood systems, balancing demand and response dynamics, and incorporating Building Integrated Photovoltaics, HVAC technologies, energy storage solutions and electric vehicle charging stations.

Importantly, DTs of a built environment evolve over time, by ingesting data from smart meters and a variety of data sources including urban platforms. A data ingestion mechanism can feed the DT models by being tied either directly into physical sensor networks or databases that store building relevant information, such as BIM models. Changes happening in the real-world can systematically update the virtual models, so as to provide better insights through the simulation of what-if scenarios. In parallel, a dynamic sensing-response loop controlled by a Dynamic Data-Driven Application System between the physical and the virtual models, can actuate smart sensors to control the physical environment. Apart for the operational phase of a building, DTs can assist in optimising the whole lifecycle of a building, covering construction, renovation and retrofitting phases through predictive analytics and data-driven decision making. The combination of DTs with blockchain technology can ensure end-to-end visibility and monitoring of targeted values, (e.g. efficiency KPIs), whilst supporting different stakeholders across the value chain to contribute to local/global sustainability goals - residents can optimise energy use, construction companies can monitor materials' lifecycles to design circular-economy strategies, authorities

can implement measures that promote energy efficiency, facility managers can extend service life and increase building's service efficiency.

D. Blockchains

A buildings management ecosystem can be simulated with a distributed network of untrusted stakeholders who however have common interests. Such a network inherits all of the distributed systems' characteristics and advantages, but also their challenges and limitations. The Blockchain technology can play a pivotal role, addressing most of these challenges by enabling trusted interactions and extended transparency in the storage, retrieval and sharing of data across the network.

Blockchain is a disruptive technology introduced by Bitcoin [28] which enables a distributed currency without a central entity (like a bank or a government) with security and transaction irreversibility guaranteed through cryptography. Ethereum [29] is the next big project that emerged, which extended Bitcoin's baseline technology creating the first programmable blockchain, by offering smart contracts support, thus extending the reach of the system well beyond finance. In the next years, multiple blockchain frameworks came to light expanding the range of possible use cases to the supply chain [30], the management of healthcare records [31], the identity management [32], the protection against fake news and lately the Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs) [33] for ensuring the authenticity of products.

Discussing NFTs, they have been widely criticized for their impact on the environment [34], as were initially run on Ethereum and all of the transactions associated with minting them were processed through a Proof-of-Work (PoW) consensus mechanism. In addition, creating an NFT was also costly due to the fact that the Ethereum network was congested with activity as a consequence of their surging popularity. Very recently, solutions based on Ethereum sidechains and other Layer 2 (L2) blockchain protocols promise the limitation of the NFTs' energy footprint compared to Proof of Work-based blockchain networks and provide artists and application developers with a more sustainable solution today, while Ethereum upgrades to Proof of Stake¹. By moving the transactions away from the Ethereum mainnet, L2 solutions can process transactions at a higher speed, at a lower cost and with significantly less energy consumption.

1) *The potential of DLT and blockchain for enhanced climate action:* In 2017 the UN recognised the potential of distributed ledger technology (DLT) and blockchain technology to contribute to enhanced climate action and sustainability through [35]:

- strengthened monitoring, reporting and verification of the impacts of climate action
- improved transparency, traceability and cost-effectiveness of climate action
- building trust among climate actors

- making incentive mechanisms for climate action accessible to the poorest
- support mobilization of green finance.

The European Commission has designed a Blockchain strategy as the driving force for making the EU an innovator in blockchain and home to significant platforms, applications and companies [12]. The 'gold standard' that embraces European values and ideas in its regulatory and legal framework suggests that Blockchain technology should:

- be sustainable and energy-efficient.
- be compatible with, and where possible support, Europe's strong data protection and privacy regulations.
- respect and enhance Europe's evolving digital Identity framework including being compatible with e-signature regulations, such as eIDAS, and supporting a sensible, pragmatic decentralised and self-sovereign identity framework.
- be able to provide high levels of cybersecurity.
- be interoperable between themselves and with legacy systems in the outside world.

One of the most significant parts of this strategy is the promotion of Blockchain for sustainability whereby the use of Blockchain technology in fostering sustainable economic development, addressing climate change, and the European Green Deal are supported. Another important part of the strategy is the support of interoperability and standardisation, contributing to the relevant work of ISO TC 307, ETSI ISG PDL, CEN-CENELEC JTC19 and IEEE and in ITU-T bodies.

III. OUR PROPOSAL

In this section, we introduce the Trusted DBL concept, the architecture and its main building blocks, and subsequently explain the data flows within the architecture.

A. Conceptualization

DTs and Blockchain is an invaluable combination of technologies that can be leveraged to achieve trustworthy and intelligent decision making in the Building Management domain. They, together with the DBLs, serve as the three pillars of the proposed Trusted DBL blueprint architecture which brings together building owners, occupants, actors of the architecture engineering and construction (AEC) sector, technology providers, financial institutions and public authorities for the creation of a green building economy. The Trusted DBL architecture employs digital building twins for virtual troubleshooting and predictive maintenance, a private permissioned blockchain network as the decentralized infrastructure to store and share the DBL data and finally interoperable NFTs for credibility and trust.

The main building blocks of the blueprint architecture are described below:

1) *Blockchain and Smart Contracts:* The Trusted DBL architecture features a hybrid blockchain scheme to combine the best of both worlds; scalability and identity verification of private blockchains as well as trust and decentralisation of public blockchains. The architecture enables end-users to

¹Ethereum 2.0, <https://ethereum.org/en/upgrades/>

Fig. 1. Overview of the Trusted DBL Ecosystem

store energy consumption and GHG emissions-related data for buildings on a private Blockchain for confidentiality and security and at the same time to issue NFTs on a public Blockchain for increased accountability and transparency.

Furthermore, and in addition to energy performance data, the private blockchain stores buildings' metadata, enabling this way the unified, systematic, well-organised and standardised monitoring of buildings' performance across a wider area, city or region. Towards complying with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [36], sensible data are kept off-chain and hosted by different stakeholders in their databases (e.g. BIMs and certificates stored in the corresponding department of the local authority) while only pointers (links) to them are stored on-chain. Meanwhile, smart contracts automate and standardise the process of gathering measurements and reporting them on-chain to be accessed by all the involved stakeholders.

2) *NFTs*: The Trusted DBL NFTs open up an energy performance marketplace that introduces new business models between the stakeholders of the entire building value chain. They follow open standards (ERC-721 [37]) to ensure their interoperability across different blockchain technologies and allow the horizontal auditability across buildings clusters by local authorities. They are minted on L2 public blockchain networks to ensure energy efficiency, by authorities who are also members of the private blockchain network and audit the energy-related records of each cluster. A decentralized marketplace is established on top of this mechanism that is used for incentivising actors of the ecosystem towards lower energy emissions actions and reliable data reporting.

3) *Digital Twins*: DTs comprise a set of models describing different aspects of the physical building, including its energy systems and in their simpler form have the capability to a) use historical in combination with ingested real-time energy emissions data, to run simulations and indicate those parameters/configurations of the energy systems that can ensure

Fig. 2. Transaction Flow in the Trusted DBL

optimal energy performance and GHG emissions minimisation, and b) actuate smart devices to adapt e.g. heating and cooling systems' performance in case regulatory energy emission thresholds are exceeded.

B. Transaction Flow and data models

1) *Updating the DBL*: As shown in Fig. 2, the Trusted DBL is being fed with data from multiple sources in order to realistically represent the physical building to the virtual space. First, AEC actors store in their own databases data related to the entire building's life-cycle (design, construction, operation and post-occupancy), such as design documents, materials used, standards followed, safety plans, maintenance reports and certificates. Only anonymised pointers to them are stored on-chain, as trusted metadata of a building accompanied by its regulatory energy performance KPIs. In addition, measurements from smart meters and other IoT devices are being continuously fed through the IoT infrastructure to the platform, to provide a near real-time monitoring of the building.

An example of the data model of a building as stored in the regional blockchain is shown below:

```

uuid (unique identifier):    string
geoposition:                json object
certificates_id:            string
maintenance_id:             string
materials_id:               string
energy_consumption:         array

```

2) *Digital Twin*: The DT's combines AI models and trains them having as input historical data, IoT data coming from the building as well as data from external sources such as weather forecast and trusted data from the blockchain to increase the trustworthiness of the models computations.

3) *Reflect DT's feedback*: Consequently, the DT simulates the building's operation and predicts emergencies, recommends maintenance actions and invokes actuators (e.g. turning off the heating) deployed in the physical space towards a more energy-efficient operation.

4) *Blockchain-based monitoring and evaluation*: The Smart Contracts deployed in the private permissioned blockchain network (e.g. Hyperledger Fabric) of a region consume the energy performance measurements ingested in

the Trusted DBL virtual space and automatically compute the energy footprint of the building. Consequently and based on the building's energy KPIs stored on-chain, the smart contracts issue NFTs to public and energy-efficient L2 blockchain protocols in order to achieve transparency, immutability and interoperability.

5) *NFTs use cases*: The interoperable NFTs enable a plethora of possible use cases for the stakeholders of the building value chain. AEC actors prove the accomplishment of an energy KPI by simply presenting their NFTs to an authority, while they also use an NFT to receive tax reliefs from the government. Even more, NFTs are exchangeable for services in the local markets e.g. free sharing of electric vehicles in the cluster.

IV. RELATED WORK

A. Global applications of DLT and blockchain for climate reporting

The pioneering example of how the global application of Blockchain and other emerging technologies, such as IoT, big data and machine learning, can help the world keep a transparent accounting system while trying to achieve the climate targets of the Paris Agreement is the Open Climate project [38]. It is an open source initiative of the Yale Open Innovation Lab together with a growing network of collaborators. The Open Climate platform maps climate actors and their associated records (i.e. countries, companies, individuals) in a shared network and through DLT and other cryptographic tools achieves: general transparency alongside individual data privacy, prevention of double counting in the trading of climate actions and digital certification, a platform for contractual automation of rules and mechanisms with financial nature such as Paris Agreement stocktakes, carbon pricing and rewards for mitigation outcomes. Software development efforts are comprised of three main components [39]: 1) a decentralized server hosting a cross-platform web application able to integrate multiple existing climate related platforms interoperating with common functions and reconciled records. 2) consolidated protocols and standards that enable an interoperable and multi-layers climate accounting ecosystem, and the required governance mechanism to achieve and maintain it. 3) a climate portal for multi-stakeholder users interface and interaction with the global accounting system, either via their integrated platforms or directly via the web application.

B. Performance-based (smart) contracts

In a recent study, [8] demonstrated the first full-stack proof-of-concept of a thermal performance-based smart contract in the built environment. In this prototype, the Ethereum blockchain is integrated with the Siemens building twin platform [40] which acts as the single source for both static (i.e. design and construction BIM IFC files) and dynamic data fetched from the sensors of a real-life physical twin.

Although successful in showing the feasibility of both the concept and the implemented technical architecture, it was found that in order to be scalable and secure for real-world

implementations, both building DTs and blockchain need to become more mature. It was also acknowledged that a public blockchain for storing data comes with its drawbacks related to transaction cost, privacy and performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The building sector is one of the great contributors to climate change. Climate policy is aimed at accelerating the decarbonization of the building stock through a green and digital transition and local authorities have a prominent role in the implementation of local sustainable energy policies and effectively play a key role in the achievement of the EU's energy and climate objectives.

Data-driven services that can facilitate processes such as predictive maintenance or monitoring of KPIs that are required for climate policy compliance are useful tools in the hands of the local authorities as they facilitate the collection of quality data and perform rigorous calculations and reporting required for climate neutrality policy impact assessment, monitoring and reporting. However, storing and sharing information among interested stakeholders, might generate critical privacy and trust issues.

Both the privacy of confidential data and the transparency to authorities and value-chain actors that wish to have a real-time overview of building stock performance at a local or regional level can be tackled through a dynamic record at facility level that segregates static and monitored data. This paper proposes a blueprint architecture for the Trusted DBL that offers such a dynamic and trusted record.

The Trusted DBL relies on the integration with state-of-the-art and emerging technologies of Blockchain and DT. It facilitates the tokenisation (NFTs) of energy emissions data in buildings that follows open standards, ensuring interoperability between blockchain networks and horizontal auditability and consistency among buildings clusters. The unified, systematic, well-organised and standardised gathering and storage of building related data across a defined area (buildings cluster) provides a schema for transparent, trusted and informed decision making and information sharing within the building's value chain and for climate neutrality policy impact assessment, monitoring and reporting.

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